

Scaling up open access publishing through transformative agreements: results from 2019 to 2022

A case study by Ciaran Hoogendoorn and Gaynor Redvers-Mutton

12/9/2023

Biochemical Society

Mailing address:

1 Naoroji Street, London WC1X 0GB

Registered address:

First Floor, 10 Queen Street Place, London EC4R 1BE

+44 (0)20 3880 2793

www.biochemistry.org

Portland Press Limited

Mailing address:

1 Naoroji Street, London WC1X 0GB

Registered address:

First Floor, 10 Queen Street Place, London EC4R 1BE

+44 (0)20 3880 2795

www.portlandpress.com

Introduction

The Biochemical Society publishes seven journals, two of which are fully gold open access (OA) titles. By the end of 2022, with 3 years of transformative Read & Publish (R&P) deals, more than half of all content in the five hybrid journals had been published OA under a CC-BY license. Greater OA uptake in certain regions prompted a deeper dive comparison to isolate success factors and to explore the degree to which we as a publisher might replicate these positive impacts globally. The regional biases may be recognisable by others in our sector. Responses to these trends will be varied. We conclude with why we are APC (article publishing charge)-cautious and provide the reasons motivating a greater drive towards institutionally-funded OA models.

Regions

For this analysis three contrasting regions were selected, with some geographically disparate regions grouped together based on shared characteristics.

- The first regional grouping is that of UK, Australia and New Zealand
- The second is USA and Canada
- The third is China

Region 1: UK, Australia and New Zealand

Although geographically very distinct regions these have been aggregated for the sake of this analysis as they are the countries where early transformative agreements (TAs) were negotiated with consortia on a national level - with Jisc in the UK and CAUL in Australia and New Zealand. These partnerships were hugely important for the Society in developing the R&P offering, as well as driving uptake when initially launched as pilots in 2020. By 2022 there were 17 CAUL institutions and 36 Jisc institutions signed up, and the proportion of articles from these countries published OA had increased significantly to almost 85% in 2022, up from around 40% in 2019. The increase in OA publications was most dramatic in Australia and New Zealand where the proportion of OA articles rose from less than a quarter in 2019 to 87% in 2022. Whilst usage from UK R&P institutions doubled between 2020 and 2022, the dramatic increase didn't extend to Australasia. Institutions in Region 1 who joined in 2020¹ published three and a half times more OA articles in 2021 than they did in 2019. At the same time, R&P spend for these institutions in 2022 was only around 4% higher than their total spend across subscriptions and APCs 4 years earlier in 2019 – well below inflation or legacy subscription price increases. For this same cohort of institutions in 2019 the total spend (across subscriptions and APCs) per OA article published was around £4650 and by 2021 total spend (on R&P agreements) per OA article had dropped to around £1350.

¹ This refers to the subset of institutions from this region with existing subscriptions who signed R&P agreements in 2020 and remained subscribed thereafter (and excludes 1 institution from this region that signed up in 2020 but subsequently unsubscribed and since then has been spending higher fees on APCs).

Figure 1: OA growth in Region 1 - Proportion of articles by access type for authors from UK, Australia and New Zealand between 2019 and 2022

The numerous success factors we attribute to growth of OA in this region can be grouped under two headings:

1. Publisher and consortium factors
 - a. National consortia helped to frame agreements with standardised licence terms and reporting templates. The R&P model we created was simple to administer, low-maintenance and uncapped in line with [Society Publishers' Coalition](#) (SocPC) principles, see Appendix 1.
 - b. Each member institution of both consortium groups decided individually whether to opt in and voluntary uptake has increased year on year.
 - c. APC spend by participating institutions was completely suspended, enabling institutions a more transparent means of tracking their OA spend.
 - d. High levels of community collaboration took place to achieve common goals through the SPA-OPS initiative, resulting in a toolkit for publishers, consortia and institutions to use funded by Wellcome, UKRI (UK Research and Innovation), and the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP)².

2. External (market-driven) factors
 - a. There was a pre-existing demand for OA from researchers in the biosciences area who saw impacts of their research (citations, downloads and sharing opportunities) increase.
 - b. National policy and funder mandates provided further incentive to publish OA.

² Wise, Alicia; Estelle, Lorraine (2019). SPA-OPS – Transformative Agreement Toolkit. Wellcome Trust. Online resource. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.9805043.v1>

Region 2: USA and Canada

In North America OA, TA uptake and OA article publishing is trailing behind that of countries in Region 1. There has been a moderate increase over the period 2019 to 2022; however, in 2022 two-thirds of OA papers were still being funded by APCs. Where institutions showed a willingness to participate, agreements have been negotiated on an individual basis. In 2022 we signed our first consortium-level R&P agreement in the region with the University of California, covering all ten campuses. We are trying to forge more new relationships with the statewide or regional library consortia operating in these countries.

Figure 2: OA growth in Region 2 - Proportion of articles by access type for authors from USA and Canada between 2019 and 2022

The boost that TAs can provide is only starting to show. However, for the cohort of North American institutions who converted to R&P between 2020 and 2022, the impacts are quantifiable: usage increased by over 40% and OA publications rose almost fourfold³.

Halfway through 2023 we are hopeful that more individual institutions as well as consortium groups, particularly those who have started to support TAs with other publishers, will convert their traditional subscriptions to R&P agreements, not least because of the external forces at play:

- a. The OSTP Nelson Memo⁴ and resultant mandates from funders are likely to impact the growth trajectory of OA in the USA. We expect OA compliance here to rise significantly in the coming years.
- b. Canada's Tri-Agency Open Access Policy of 2015⁵ has not yet been updated but there may yet be top-down mandates and monitoring to accelerate OA growth in this region in line with other countries.

³ For institutions in USA and Canada who moved from standard subscriptions to R&P between 2020 and 2022: increase in OA publications as measured between 2019 and 2022 and increase in usage between 2020 and 2022 (no usage figures available for 2019).

⁴ OSTP Nelson Memo <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-access-Memo.pdf>

⁵ Tri-Agency Open Access Policy on Publications <https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/interagency-research-funding/policies-and-guidelines/open-access/tri-agency-open-access-policy-publications>

Region 3: China

OA publishing trends in China stand in stark contrast to those seen in the first two regions. Across the period of this study China started off with very high levels of OA, with 90% of articles from corresponding authors based in China published OA in 2019. This was entirely funded by APCs and concentrated mostly in a single full-OA sound science journal: *Bioscience Reports*. APC publications from authors based in China peaked in 2020 and in recent years we have seen steep declines, which we attribute to a number of factors:

1. Publisher-controlled factors
 - a. In 2019 we identified that *Bioscience Reports* had been targeted by papermills and in response more robust editorial quality control checks have been put in place. This has led to more papers being rejected and the consequent decrease in publications.
 - b. We have a subscription-only consortium deal in place, and no transformative agreements and therefore no means for driving institutionally-funded OA.
2. External (market-driven) factors
 - a. *Bioscience Reports* was put on The Early Warning List⁶ established by the Chinese Academy of Sciences. While the exact reasons were not given, we believe it may have been linked to papermill issues and the high proportion of Chinese authorship in this title. In 2021, following measures taken by the journal's editorial board, it was removed from the Early Warning List; however, since appearing on the list there has been a sustained decrease in submissions from China.
 - b. With Clarivate delisting journals in 2023⁷, there is heightened wariness and scrutiny in this region of high volume, often APC-funded fully OA sound science journals.

In 2018 over half of all OA articles published in the Society's journals were from corresponding authors based in China. By 2022, this had dropped to 17% and it is the only major region where the Society saw a decline in OA publishing over the period analysed. However, usage data showed a threefold increase for Chinese institutions between 2020 and 2022. Had a national transformative agreement been in place, offering unlimited OA publishing across all journals, instead of a standard subscription agreement, we expect the OA trend may have looked quite different.

Figure 3: OA trends in Region 3: Proportion of articles by access type for authors from China between 2019 and 2022

⁶ Early Warning List from the Chinese Academy of Sciences, <https://earlywarning.fenqubiao.com/#/en/early-warning-journal-list-2020>

⁷ Supporting integrity of the scholarly record: Our commitment to curation and selectivity in the Web of Science, blogpost from Clarivate <https://clarivate.com/blog/supporting-integrity-of-the-scholarly-record-our-commitment-to-curation-and-selectivity-in-the-web-of-science/>

Conclusion

R&P has been most effective where consortia have presented TAs collectively to a large group of institutions at once, as was the case in the UK, Australia and New Zealand.

In discussion with R&P partners, the model that we have adopted – unlimited read and uncapped OA publishing across our entire portfolio - has been welcomed. To replicate the success we have had in the first region of our analysis, we have and will continue to prioritise consortia and institutional agreements targeting regions where OA is mandated at national level, through government and funder agencies. Our organisational size and resourcing requires a targeted approach with the aim of maximising the impact of R&P and bringing fee-free OA to the largest numbers of authors.

However, there are many nations where the external market forces driving OA publication do not prevail and where our finite resourcing limits the number of agreements we can hope to negotiate at any one time.

The evidence presented in this case study has strengthened the Society's commitment to facilitate more institutionally-funded OA models, enabling ever more of our authors to publish OA fee-free. The APC model conflicts with a value system that is based on equity and inclusion. Furthermore, we have also experienced the volatility and vulnerability to exploitation that an author-funded model presents. We are therefore planning the introduction of Subscribe to Open in 2025 to run alongside our R&P models, which will help to achieve further immediate open access at scale through institutional support networks.

Appendix 1

Society Publishers' Coalition endorsed transformative agreement framework

Unlimited Open Access

Some of our members offer Read and Publish deals and have worked together to align these transformative offerings to the following common principles:

Unlimited Open Access

Publishers / Society Publishers that are:

- Not for profit and mission driven
- Actively transitioning away from legacy subscription models and/or piloting transformative approaches

Agreements:

- Offer unlimited OA for all eligible publications *plus* read access to paywall content
- Any paper eligible under the deal from a corresponding author at a participating institution is included
- Authors and readers are notified of institutional participation to facilitate OA
- Meta-data driven annual reporting for librarians
- Creative Commons licensing
- No NDAs – terms are transparent and publicly available (e.g. agreements deposited on ESAC)

This is one of several routes to sustainable OA in use by SocPC members.